

Limited Urban Citizenship: The Case of Community Councils in East Jerusalem

Abstract: Urban environments are often disputed over issues of class, gender, ethnicity, and race. Urban citizenship within such spaces has been found to be fragmented, or even 'dark.' Intermediary organizations that represent spatially concentrated communities often operate under these contentious circumstances. This paper focuses on the role of intermediary institutions in the contested city of (East) Jerusalem. Building on in-depth interviews and site visits, we suggest that CCs implement a limited form of urban citizenship via a range of functions that vary from service provision to political representation. We explain the process by which this form of urban citizenship is created and operated, and highlight the precarity of the concept in a non-democratic context where most people are stateless residents. Through this case, we seek to enrich the literature on urban citizenship and CCs in contested cities with an emphasis on the multiple urban and national logics that operate in space.

Keywords: Community Councils, Urban citizenship, East Jerusalem, Contested cities, Participation

Introduction

In the last few decades, scholars have produced a great deal of research that examines the power of urban institutions and residents to shape their lives in meaningful ways (Marcuse 2009; Mitchell 2003; Novy and Colomb 2013). Cities have been celebrated as

platforms for progressive politics, tolerance, and democratic participation (Brenner, Marcuse, and Mayer 2011; Barber 2013). Within this discourse, urban citizenship has emerged as a framework that encapsulates residents' rights and duties, as well as an alternative to nation-state citizenship (Holston 1998; Barak 2020; Baubock 2003; Staeheli et al. 2015). Notwithstanding these celebratory accounts, scholars have also noted the shortcomings of urban citizenship in settings of conflict and fragmentation (Blokland et al. 2015; Avni 2020). In many cases around the world, urban residents are not citizens of the country in which they live, and their urban residence is the only form of precarious citizenship they have (Varsanyi 2006; Yacobi 2011; Bhimji 2016; de Shalit 2018). In other cases, especially in rapidly urbanizing regions, residents may be citizens but reside informally in the city, with very limited political power and fundamental rights (Wang, Wang, and Wu 2009; Bhan 2009; Zayim 2014).

Following these varying interpretations of the city's potential as a political institution, our study is situated in the tension invoked by urban citizenship as both a coercive and emancipatory term (Wood 2014). We examine the role of an intermediary governance structure – the Community Council in Jerusalem (CC henceforth) – in fostering urban citizenship. We ask how emergent types of urban citizenship are formed via the CCs under the constraints of a deeply contested city and non-democratic conditions. We focus on East Jerusalem, the Palestinian part of the city, where the vast majority of residents are not citizens of Israel (or any other country) and experience a significant democratic deficit, despite the fact that Israel oversees almost all aspects of their lives (Shlomo 2017; Alkhalili 2019). Their residency status is continuously contested, uncertain, and precarious. To be sure, the CC is only one path among many to

be civically engaged in Jerusalem, and we do not suggest that it is necessarily the ideal one. But it is a useful case study since the CC is a hybrid institution, i.e., part-government and part-community, and it encompasses the continuous tensions that East-Jerusalemites experience daily given their highly unstable status in the city.

Building on in-depth interviews and site visits, we answer the research question by discussing the paradoxical reality in which the CC in East Jerusalem operates: it seemingly gives Palestinian residents a voice in the municipality and access to resources, yet is simultaneously viewed as an arm of the Israeli occupation. We suggest that despite the myriad constraints engendered by the politics of a divided city, the CC offers East-Jerusalemite Palestinians an opportunity and pragmatic path towards claiming their *limited urban citizenship*. We envision limited urban citizenship as a process of civic engagement whereby structural constraints and unequal access to opportunities prevent residents from fully claiming their right to the city. Under these circumstances, residents take an active part in some struggles while occasionally refrain from the national political struggle.

By analyzing urban citizenship as an ongoing, everyday process rather than as a defined set of haves and haves-not, we highlight both its emancipatory and 'dark' sides. Our contribution to knowledge is thus twofold. First, we examine urban citizenship in an environment that is fragmented not only by the classic elements of class, race, gender, and religion—like in many other cities worldwide—but also by an ethno-national conflict that shapes the citizenship status of the city's minority population.

Second, while much of the current research on urban citizenship engages with community mobilizations and "bottom-up initiatives to govern cities" (Gillespie and Nguyen 2019, 978), we examine it through the perspective of a semi-institutionalized body in a non-democratic context. We offer a new understanding of how city institutions help build urban citizenship. Similar to previous observations about 'bottom-up' mobilizations, the hybrid structure of the CC reveals a process of expanding and deepening residents' civic activity. We suggest that that this process is assisted the CC's semi-institutional character that facilitates access, albeit often limited, to city resources that non-citizens are typically unable to obtain under conditions of political oppression

The paper is structured as follows. We start with a literature review on urban citizenship and community councils. We then lay out the research design and methods, including key background about East Jerusalem and Community Councils in the city. Next, we present the different strategies that the councils employ and discuss their implications for urban citizenship. We conclude with a discussion on community councils and urban citizenship in Jerusalem and other contested cities, and note the councils' conflictual role as well as the multiple logics that affect their *modus operandi*.

Urban citizenship: A literature review

In the last two decades, urban citizenship has emerged as a leading term and analytic lens in critical urban studies. Many scholars have attributed this process to the 'rescaling' of the state's configuration worldwide, in which the nation-state is weakening while the 'global' and 'local' scales are gaining prominence (Blank 2007; Wood 2014; Baubock 2003). Like national 'citizenship,' urban citizenship is an intricate concept, pervaded with

multiple formal and informal meanings (Staeheli 2003; Baubock 2003). Unlike national citizenship, urban citizenship is not rooted in one's passport or country of origin, but rather in local residency. Ostensibly, the local scale invokes a shared sense of purpose, practices, and values among residents (although, as we note later, this notion has been contested). The 'urban' is what gives citizenship its spatial dimension; the struggles for urban citizenship that transpire in various public and private urban arenas such as homes, parks, and squares, both shape, and are shaped by, the physical and social geography of the city (Pérez 2017; Staeheli 2003). However, beyond the general notion that urban citizenship may give residents more access to decision-making processes, the bundle of rights and responsibilities that makes up urban citizenship is still relatively ambiguous.

While there is no single agreed-upon definition of the term and what it encapsulates, an important research strand has viewed urban citizenship as a *process* (Staeheli 2003; Varsanyi 2006). In this view, urban citizenship is not a fixed status, but a lived experience that acquires significance and constantly evolves through interaction with the social, economic, political, and cultural forces that operate in space (Phillips 2015). In this dynamic, situated process, residents—whether individuals or groups—negotiate their place in the city (Cohen and Margalit 2015). These residents often belong to marginalized and disadvantaged communities that fight for inclusion and recognition, with varying degrees of success (Avni and Yiftachel 2014; Millstein 2017; Jabareen 2014).

The 'dark side' of urban citizenship?

Although there is a tendency in the literature to celebrate the achievements of such struggles, as well as the potential of urban citizenship to secure benefits and counteract

exclusion, some scholars urge caution when analyzing the local scale. While participation is essential and valued, it may not necessarily lead to just outcomes since some individuals and groups can suppress others' claims in the process (Purcell 2006; Fainstein 2010; Avni 2019). Blokland et al. (2015) similarly suggest that urban struggles often exhibit splintering and fragmentation between the claims of competing groups that occasionally reinforce, rather than resolve, existing power hierarchies. Moreover, the voices of the marginalized are often ignored by several layers of government institutions that exercise their authority to deprive residents of their right to the city (Bhan 2009). Indeed, the politics of citizenship are not necessarily benevolent, as citizens are often discriminated against based on ethnicity, race, economic status, or religion both in the national and urban spheres (Yiftachel 2009; Brøgger 2019; Blokland et al. 2015). Similarly, the city is not necessarily a progressive institution, and it can be a center of oppression, discrimination, and violence (Secor 2004; Greenberg Raanan and Avni 2020; Duru 2019). Nevertheless, scholars maintain that despite the relevant critiques about urban citizenship and its weaknesses, the hope for inclusive and equal urban citizenship is all but lost (Bollens 2007; Hays 2010; Yiftachel 2016).

Urban citizenship in the absence of national citizenship

Another area in which conceptualizations of urban citizenship might encounter difficulties are situations where longtime urban residents are non-citizens of the nation-state in which they live (Varsanyi 2006). While citizenship (or city-zenship) was historically linked to residency in the city (Wood 2014), at present, formal citizenship hinges upon (though is not automatically granted upon) living in a nation-state. However, in a growing number of cases around the world, urban residents are not legal citizens of

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the city or country in which they reside, but are rather undocumented migrants, refugees or homeland minorities without citizenship (e.g., the case of East Jerusalem Palestinians) (Ridgley 2008; Varsanyi 2006; Cohen and Margalit 2015; Wang, Wang, and Wu 2009).

Some cities in the US and Europe function as a sanctuary and provide shelter and protection to non-citizens through legislation that grants access to services regardless of citizenship status (Varsanyi 2006; Darling 2017; de-Shalit 2018). While sanctuary cities are typically perceived as progressive, a critical perception stresses that the governmental structures that protect the non-citizens are an additional means to secure the 'public good.' Thus, the intentions of sanctuary cities are not entirely benevolent (Darling 2017; Rokem, 2016). In other cases, like some ethno-nationally contested cities, e.g., Belfast, Nicosia, and Sarajevo, residents might have citizenship, but not one they necessarily identify with. In these cities, decisions regarding the use of public resources are embroiled in political decisions over identity (Bar 2019; Hays 2010). On the other hand, Bollens (2007) notes that urban citizenship might emerge as a positive framework that facilitates negotiation and bridging conflicts, as, for example, was discovered to be the case in Belfast (Hays, 2010). Still, in Jerusalem, most Palestinian residents do not hold any formal citizenship—similar to the case of immigrants in sanctuary cities, yet under entirely different circumstances. Our case study of Community Councils in East Jerusalem seeks to contribute to the theorization of this situation, focusing on the role of intermediary organizations in fostering a sense of limited urban citizenship.

Community Councils

Community Councils exist in various configurations across the world, under several titles, e.g., neighbourhood associations, organizations, and community enterprises. While their political role, composition, finance and administrative structures vary greatly, CCs around the world share important characteristics that make a comparison between them instrumental. As an intermediary governance tier situated between the local government and the public (Coaffee and Healey 2003; Yinon-Amoyal and Kallus 2005), they play an influential role in local decision-making processes and are uniquely positioned to influence city policies on a neighbourhood scale (King 2004). The functions of CCs and their domains of engagement are also diverse and include land-use planning, health, education, crime prevention, and more (Jun and Musso 2013; Durose and Lowndes 2010). CCs can be formed from 'above' or 'below': whereas some can be considered as grassroots organizations since they are non-profit, volunteer-run (Smith 2000), others are financed by municipalities and are moored in institutionalized settings (Kathi and Cooper 2005).

Within the existing literature on CCs, an urban citizenship lens has rarely been employed to examine them, although their role in fostering civic engagement has been studied. CCs are assumed to enable public involvement in neighborhood affairs and to constitute an important pillar of civil society (Musso et al. 2006; Bailey 2012). Studies conducted on community-based-organizations in Boston and on Neighbourhood Associations in Chicago found that they superseded city officials as the legitimate representatives of poor neighbourhoods and were able to effectively channel resources to

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their respective communities (Levine 2016; Park, Mosley, and Grogan 2018). Similarly, other studies, mostly in the US and the UK, examined how CCs have assisted in building social capital, thereby enhancing a sense of community and encouraging public participation in city affairs (Anderson, Blair, and Shirk 2018).

However, scholars have also pointed out potential weaknesses in the function and impact of CCs. One key challenge is the issue of representation. CCs may serve the parochial interests of the more dominant constituencies that neither represent nor account for the needs and concerns of other less engaged groups that live in the neighborhood (Park, Mosley, and Grogan 2018). Other challenges might include legitimacy, especially, but not limited to, fragmented communities or societies (Benit-Gbaffou and Katsaura, 2014). While many studies acknowledge the context of economic and racial segregation in which the CCs are situated, very little research has accounted for the CCs' role in fostering urban citizenship in ethno-nationally divided cities, especially among non-citizens. In the next section, we will outline the Jerusalem setting and explain the convoluted political circumstances that serve as the backdrop for CCs' activity in the city.

Research design and methodology

The setting: East Jerusalem

East Jerusalem is the popular term for the Palestinian neighbourhoods within Jerusalem, and derives its name from its position East of the 1949 Armistice border (the Green Line). Following the 1967 War, Israel annexed Jordanian Al-Quds/Jerusalem and villages surrounding the city and included them under the Jerusalem municipality jurisdiction.

The international law considers East Jerusalem an occupied territory. During the years

since 1967 Israel has made intense efforts to deepen its control over this territory by simultaneously building Jewish neighborhoods east of the Green Line while heavily limiting housing permits for Palestinian neighbourhoods (Shlay and Rosen 2010; Chiodelli 2013). The latter have also suffered from degraded infrastructure, disinvestment, house demolitions, and a severe lack of services such as schools and healthcare clinics. About 400,000 Palestinians live today in Jerusalem, comprising 38% of the city's population. The majority of them are permanent residents and not citizens, subjected to a permanent state of gray space (Avni and Yiftachel 2014)—neither entirely included in, or excluded from, Israel. According to the "center of life" policy enforced by the Israeli government, they must prove that they continuously live in Jerusalem, or else their residency status might be revoked (Salem 2018).

Since the construction of the Separation Wall beginning in 2002, the population density in the Palestinian neighbourhoods located on the Israeli side of the wall has further risen and daily life has become more challenging (Samman 2018). At the same time, a growing disconnect from the West Bank has rendered these neighbourhoods more dependent on Jerusalem's economy and services. As a large number of East-Jerusalemites work in West Jerusalem and consume services there, daily life has been increasingly characterized by encounters between Palestinians and Israelis (Feitelson and Cohen-Blankshtain 2018, Shtern and Yacobi 2019; Rokem and Vaughan 2018). Still, most Palestinians boycott the municipal elections despite their eligibility to vote, and collaboration with the Israeli government—commonly referred to as normalization of the occupation—is a contested issue. We will now turn to describe the CCs in this polarized reality.

Community Councils in Jerusalem

This study focuses on the role of CCs in a deeply divided city. The CC is an intermediary governance structure that was first established in Jerusalem in the 1970s and further institutionalized in the early 1990s. The rationale for its establishment was the need to manage a rapidly growing city, especially after the 1967 War. Under Mayor Kollek's administration (1965-1993), the strategy was to advance decentralization of social service delivery to "promote social harmony in a culturally divided city" as well as to ensure the legitimacy of the local government (Hasson and Ley 1997, 37). The CC operates in a hybrid, two-tier system. The first layer is the professional staff (40% of the NC's composition) that work under the auspices of the Israeli Association of Community Centers (IACC), a non-profit governmental organization. Founded in 1969, the IACC operates under the auspices of the Ministry of Education and Culture and its main mission is to build and develop a network of sustainable communities across the country (IACC 2020). The second layer (60%) is a community council, which is an independent legal association operating under the 1980 Associations Law (Yinon-Amoyal and Kallus 2005). The CCs serve both as institutions in charge of representing residents concerning various municipal issues, as well as the providers of recreational facilities (Zaban 2016).

Community Councils in East Jerusalem

The background for the establishment of the CCs in East Jerusalem lies in two distinct policy-paths: governance-oriented and conflict-oriented (Bollens 2007). According to the former, the CCs' establishment was part of an all-city reform to improve municipal services and empower local democracy (Schmidt 1997). By the latter, they serve a

political agenda in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict as another act of Israeli control (Schmidt and Hatem 2008). Since CCs were imposed upon the Palestinian residents, Palestinians have often identified them as a misguided attempt to 'normalize' the contentious relations between the two sides.

Out of 30 CCs in Jerusalem, only five are located in East Jerusalem: Beit Safafa, Beit David, A-Tur, A-Thuri, and Beit Hanina, which includes three branches: Issawia, Kufr Aqab, and Shuafat (see Figure 1 and Table 1). Each CC is led by an elected board from the community that nominates the chair. The managers are appointed by the municipality and IACC, which finances their salary. The councils' roles revolve around three main aspects: (1) physical – urban planning and development of local infrastructure, (2) services – such as education, culture, and sports and (3) community development, mostly, social capital and leadership training (Hasson, Schori, and Adiv 1995; Schmidt 1997). After many years of having been managed by external employees—the majority of whom are non-Jerusalemite Israeli Palestinians—in recent years, more and more senior staff are locals.

Figure 1: Map of Community Councils in East Jerusalem

Table 1: Community Councils in East Jerusalem: Distribution, budget and structure

In theory, the CCs in East Jerusalem are like their counterparts in West Jerusalem—both confront tensions regarding issues of representation and legitimacy. In practice, considerable differences exist among them. Since they are primarily funded and administered by the Jerusalem Municipality and the IACC, the CCs in East Jerusalem are perceived by many residents as an arm of the Israeli occupation, similar to other governmental institutions (Shlomo 2017). Even though the CCs' staff is Palestinian, and the activities are tailored to the local population, many would consider engagement with the CCs as part of the so-called normalization of the occupation and would hesitate to partake in their activities.

Another complex issue confronting CCs is the lack of national citizenship of East-Jerusalemite Palestinians—a status that denies them the right to vote in national elections. Although permitted to vote in municipal elections, most Palestinian residents boycott these local elections to avoid recognizing Israel's legitimacy (Blake et al. 2018). In a reality where most East Jerusalemites are not citizens and must continuously prove their eligibility to live in the city, and where they face home demolitions and occasional violence, issues of trust and legitimacy are paramount to the CCs success, yet are further complicated by a lack of established and unanimous political leadership in East Jerusalem (El Kurd 2018). For example, for reasons of (mis)trust, external board members from the municipality and IACC are usually absent from board meetings, although their presence is formally required.

The status of the CCs in East Jerusalem is intertwined with their respective neighbourhoods—among the poorest and most underinvested in the city. They suffer from congestion, longtime neglect, and degraded infrastructure and services such as sewage overflows, broken sidewalks, lack of public transportation, and insufficient waste collection (Miodownik and Brenner 2018; Lehrs and Brenner 2020). In addition, the population is ranked very low in socio-economic terms on a national scale, and unemployment and poverty rates are alarming. These conditions affect the CCs in several ways. First, poor people cannot afford to pay much for services; the ability of the CCs to self-fund activities is thus severely limited. Second, the services provided by the CCs are not necessarily viewed as a priority for residents who struggle with day-to-day life challenges.

However, the CCs' existence, between this 'rock and a hard place' (Rosen and Avni 2019), offers the Palestinian residents an indirect approach to the Israeli authorities and a bridge for cooperation with or forum for opposition to the municipality. From an urban citizenship perspective, the CCs are one of the few civic paths that are available to and pursued by Palestinian residents, as well as recognized by the municipality.

Methods

Our study builds on interviews with key informants and site visits. We conducted 32 semi-structured interviews between 2018-2019 with diverse stakeholders from three main groups:

- 1) To understand the function of CCs from their own perspective, we interviewed 12 directors and chairs of boards (East-Jerusalemite Palestinians and Israeli Palestinians).

2) To understand the CC's work from 'above,' we interviewed four representatives from the IACC (Israelis and Israeli Palestinians), which partially oversees the work of the CCs.

3) To learn about how the CCs are viewed from the 'outside,' we interviewed 16 selected engaged residents who are not involved with the CCs, defined as people who are active participants in public organizations, non-profits, or neighbourhood organizations (Hays 2010) (primarily Palestinians and a few Israelis).

We asked participants about the following themes: their life histories of living in East-Jerusalem (or elsewhere) (childhood memories, adulthood, family); their work experience (career choices, achievements, challenges) and the neighbourhoods in which they live or work (characteristics, problems, leadership issues). Our affiliation as Israeli-Jewish researchers from an Israeli academic institution was made clear to all of the interviewees as we made the initial contact by phone or email. The majority of the interviews were conducted in Hebrew and a few in English. While Hebrew is the second or third language for the Palestinian interviewees, most of them spoke very-good-to-excellent Hebrew. Except for a couple of interviews, they were recorded and transcribed with the interviewees' consent. Overall, the response rate was very high.

The transcripts of the interviews and observations were processed using Atlas.TI software. Initially, we marked and tagged all the different activities that the CC facilitated in their communities. Then, through a thematic analysis process, we looked for expressions regarding the contested nature of the city (e.g., suspicion, normalization, mistrust etc.). Finally, we organized them under key categories in order to indicate the process of urban citizenship.

To complement the information from the interviews, we also spent time in the different neighbourhoods to understand their physical and social environment. We went for guided walks with professionals/ urban planners and reviewed professional reports about planning issues in Jerusalem. We also conducted informal interviews with professionals and residents whom we know through our academic and personal circles. Finally, we participated in several community events in the discussed neighbourhoods as participant-observers.

Finally, there are some limitations in the data collection regarding the number and extent of participants in the CC's activities. The CCs keep track of registration for paid activities, but we did not have access to these numbers. The number of non-paying volunteers is not documented. Collecting information in a 'gray space' such as East Jerusalem is challenging and one should be careful about generalizations from missing data. At the same time, we believe that the phenomenon under study is important even if marginal in scope due to its potential strong urban-political implications.

Findings: Urban Citizenship in a contested city

Examining the CCs from an urban citizenship lens, we find that they employ a broad spectrum of strategies to foster change in civic life. In the following section, we outline these strategies according to three categories that we envision as a continuum: service provision, community organizing, and political representation, and consider their implications for the formation of limited urban citizenship in East Jerusalem.

Service Provision

The bulk of the CCs' activity revolves around the provision of various social services in five main areas: (1) formal education, such as daycares and adult education, (2) informal education, such as language classes and teens' groups, (3) culture and sports, such as theatre, music, and sports tournaments, (4) professional development training and (5) leadership and community-building, for example, leadership programs for youths and recreational groups for the elderly. The supply and extent of these activities vary significantly across neighbourhoods. Attendance rates are influenced not only by the residents' financial status but, perhaps more importantly, by the level of opposition that each CC confronts. Even when they offer 'apolitical' activities, most of them encounter stiff opposition from the public. In an interview with the director of a CC in one of the most marginalized neighbourhoods of East-Jerusalem, the director shared an anecdote:

Once we hosted an event of inflatables At night a word came out saying that I'm *Jesusa* [traitor], that I want to work with the municipality on the unification of Jerusalem, and that's why I do this activity, to do the inflatables for the children and to forget that we are under the occupation...and we barely held the event... the kids love the inflatables but because of the publicity most people were afraid that their kids would show up.

Interviewer: how did you feel?

Respondent: I cried. I wanted to do something good for the people that the kids will enjoy and release pressure, but it didn't succeed.

(Interview, 2018)

On the other hand, we also heard many success stories of directors who managed to establish a basis of support. Another director proudly shared how the CC functions as a 'mini-municipality':

When I first took the position we were in a rented apartment, I remember, three rooms. It was so tiny and you couldn't do anything there, even socially; I mean, we are a community center. Today we operate daycares, kindergartens, extracurricular activities, groups for women, the elderly, summer camps, events, we have a gym. We are aiming to build the first swimming pool in the Arab sector, so we invested a lot in social things and progressed a lot. Today we have 200 employees. We are not a community center, we are *the* community center.

(Interview, 2019)

Some participants told us that by providing necessary services, which are otherwise hard to access in East Jerusalem, the CCs are succeeding in attracting residents. Education, in particular, was viewed as one such core service. It should be noted that education, like most other issues in East Jerusalem, is a contested topic since the education system in Jerusalem is separate for Palestinians and Israelis. However, in the last few years, there has been a notable increase in Palestinian schools that adopt the Israeli curriculum, and the number of Palestinians studying Hebrew and attending Israeli universities has also significantly increased (Shlomo 2017; Alayan, 2018). The Israeli government has been making consistent efforts to further intensify the integration of Palestinian institutions into the Israeli system through various incentives. Some of these programs, such as excellence centers for youths, are executed in collaboration with the

CCs. When we asked one of the participants why they think that educational services are widely consumed by the Palestinian public despite the contestation, they said:

"because....[one] can't give up on education... no matter what one's beliefs are."

(Interview, 2019)

At the same time, the links between the municipality and the CCs also create tremendous challenges because of the deep mistrust residents feel towards the former, and by extension, the latter. Participants informed us of various cases where collaboration between the municipality and the CC was concealed in order to carry out activities such as a street festival or a concert. One of the directors emphasized the ambivalence that residents feel:

People don't know what they're doing. They want to connect with the municipality and get services, but they don't want to do it publicly, so no one will say that they collaborate with the establishment. But when you tell them, 'but all the schools belong to the Ministry of Education, and all the health clinics operate through the Ministry of Health, you, each and every one of you, work at a job that is somehow related to the state, so how do you explain that you don't want a CC?' On the contrary, the CC is an NGO...it has a board, and the board can decide about the policy of this place. You want normalization or you object to it, it's up to you...

(Interview, 2019)

While the evidence above shows an ambiguous approach toward the CCs practices, service provision is relatively uncontested. Residents are willing to consume some of the CCs' services for reasons of self-development for themselves or their children. This could

be considered a pragmatic approach to urban citizenship under conditions of conflict, i.e., people selectively consume from among the services offered, yet refrain from adopting a more engaged position.

Community organizing

Beyond service provision, the CCs' mandate extends to community engagement and representation. In *community organizing*, we refer to mobilization practices centered around neighbourhood projects that the CC organizes with residents, i.e., activities that go beyond individual consumption of services to group-based action. These activities can be clean-ups of streets or monuments, initiation and maintenance of community gardens, place-making projects, and others. One of the interviewees gave an example of a community initiative that was contested at first, but later become legitimate and inspirational:

The neighbourhood cemetery. Thirty years ago, it was completely neglected. The walls around it were destroyed. Inside, all the vegetation was dry, [there was] no lighting, [it was] disorganized. An idea originated from a few people, 'let's change that, and it's ours' . . . and we started in the neighbourhood and I'm talking about a project that according to preliminary estimates cost 2-3 million NIS [\$570,000-860,000]. In the beginning, people said that it's forbidden and it's against religion. But whoever started working there did not listen And we started the job and the initiative with all the representatives, even though some were against it. Today everyone says, 'where were we and why did we object?' Some of the biggest opponents became highly involved in the CC.

(Interview, 2018)

This example illustrates quite vividly how the CCs are capable of setting community initiatives into action despite local dissidents. Their institutional stability allows them to take risks. In the process of internal community organizing, like the one above, good results contribute to their legitimacy inside the neighborhood and inspire more residents to become active in their community as they promote initiatives and exercise their urban citizenship.

Political representation

In *political representation*, we refer to more controversial actions, usually conducted with or against the municipality and the State. These typically revolve around urban planning and infrastructure issues. Compared to service provision, these roles are more sensitive and require a more substantial base of legitimacy and trust. This is especially true in East Jerusalem, where issues of urban planning, education, and infrastructure are inevitably political and, as such, can be risky arenas to engage with. The suspicion and mistrust towards the government are much stronger there, while the need for political and civic leadership is greater.

Since we view urban citizenship as a process rather than a fixed status, we conceptualize community organizing and political representation as a spectrum of strategies. The stronger and more legitimate the CCs become in the eyes of their respective communities, the more risks they are willing to take. While there are significant variations in the involvement of different councils in community mobilization

processes, all of the respondents share a strong sense of walking a fine line. One director said:

No matter how much the CC tries to promote, to give to the community, the suspicion is very strong. We, as directors, are in a position that no one should be envious of. We are really in a fight with all sides. We're fighting the IACC because they have projects that they want to promote because it's their interest to promote them because the Ministry of Education pressured them but we, who are in the neighbourhood with the residents, say it's not going to work. . . Also, the municipality in some of the projects, in a lot of them, we do collaborate with what we perceive as beneficial, but in many problematic projects, we fight the municipality.

(Interview, 2019)

As mentioned by the director, working against the municipality carries tremendous risks. As an intermediary governance structure, CCs all over Jerusalem are constantly situated in an awkward position (Zaban 2016; Rosen and Avni 2019). However, since most Palestinian Jerusalemites are not citizens, they are under far greater scrutiny than Israeli citizens. Even supposedly apolitical activities can be met with force by the Israeli authorities. This was the case in Beit Safafa neighbourhood, where a civic campaign involving the CC against a highway that would bifurcate the neighbourhood resulted in interrogations, arrests, police and army brutality, and the involvement of Israel Security Agency (Interview, June 2019).

Under these circumstances, it is understandable why CCs would be careful about getting involved with such struggles. And yet, some of them have. CCs have sued the municipality and the State on several occasions, initiated their own planning processes and alternative master plans, and refused to collaborate with the municipality on some projects (see Braier 2013 for examples). In some cases, taking a stand against the municipality helped the CCs to establish their authority and, eventually, build a stronger collaboration, as one director recounted his legislative struggle against the municipality over resources for the education system:

I remember the start of the court appeals against the municipality, how hard it was for them to 'swallow'...the fact that we pose a mirror to their face, go against them and humiliate them for their disinvestment, time-wasting and lies.... I say that at a certain point, maybe four or five years after the beginning, the municipality realized that our pressure helped, rather than damaged, them to get budgets from the government. So now we see a positive change, as they started to collaborate with us behind the scenes

(Interview, 2018).

This quotation emphasizes the potential of some CCs to serve as meaningful arenas for civic engagement.

Yiftachel (2016, 488) notes that "resistance in Jerusalem, like most cities, is often practiced through mundane, micro-practices, and unlike its portrayal in the media, it is rarely heroic or violent." Similarly, we found that only selected CCs are in a position to pursue political campaigns and launch their own planning initiatives. A degree of savvy

and practicality is required when deciding what projects to pursue and in which activities to participate. For those CCs in a more politically tenuous position, explicit political campaigns carry too big a risk. Thus, a number of interviewees demonstrated both agency and caution in how they prioritized their interventions and needs. "If the CC says that it doesn't want a certain project, this project will not take place," clarified one director, referring to any project that the municipality would want to initiate with them. He emphasized that East-Jerusalemites are tired of empty words and broken promises. Thus, one of his strategies as a director is to start a new project only when he is confident that the project is funded and feasible. For example, since the issue of land disputes is one of the most contested issues in Jerusalem (Jabareen 2017), the CC's approach is to avoid collaborating with the municipality where disputed lands are involved:

We as a CC don't want to be in the picture [in such cases] because if we were involved with land registration and ended up with not one percent, but even half percent, of expropriated land that belonged to someone, the CC will be burnt down and we'll have to start all over again. . . it's a very complicated area, very intricate, there is a lot of suspicions.

He added:

. . . You'd be surprised that sometimes they call us to annul a ticket given by the police. So they see us as the police, on the one hand, also the municipality and the Ministry of Interior because...every institution like us... the suspicion is strong, and we will take care of ourselves as a CC if we choose only the projects that do

good to East Jerusalem. If there is any suspicion, we won't be there, because the residents don't want us to be there either.

(Interview, 2019)

As a way of conceptualizing the CCs' role in foregrounding urban citizenship, we suggest the following model as a representation of the emerging urban citizenship's various aspects (Figure 2). The pyramid shape of the model illustrates the limited scope of the residents' urban citizenship. At the base of the pyramid, we place service provision, the most basic and least contested function that CCs offer. Above it, we locate community organizing. At the top of the pyramid lies political representation, which is considered to be highly contested by the CC and the residents alike. The right side of the Figure illustrates these modes with examples from the CCs in East Jerusalem. The axis on the left of the model describes the residents' involvement. As they move up along the pyramid through the different modes, their level and form of participation intensifies and their role shifts from mere consumers of services to actively engaged residents.

Figure 2: A conceptual three-tier model of limited urban citizenship in East Jerusalem's CCs.

Conclusion: Limited Urban citizenship in a contested city

Our study aims to elucidate that despite the conflicted position of CCs in East Jerusalem, they play a key role in advancing a limited form of urban citizenship. We argue that an urban citizenship framework is necessary and useful in the East Jerusalem context because in the absence of state citizenship and given the difficulties to participate at the city level, participation at the mid-urban scale is an important form of engagement. While CCs are partly grounded in institutional settings, their role should not be confused with a 'municipality writ-small.' They are shaped to a large extent by residents' involvement, are often on the opposite sides with the municipality, and allow residents various degrees

of participation, from presumably apolitical services to more controversial actions within the urban, rather than the national, scale.

One could argue that the CC's setting and its inherent limitations lead to a coercive form of urban citizenship, where membership in the city hinges upon collaboration with the government—the 'dark side' of urban citizenship. It may indeed be the case. We do not wish to idealize the CCs model nor glorify it, and we certainly recognize that some CCs have more limited capabilities than others. From an institutional perspective, the CCs are constrained not only by their politically contested status but also by the municipality, which does not grant them full independence (Rosen and Avni 2019). From the residents' side, the CCs enable participation and access to public goods yet at the cost of collaboration with the Municipality and the Israeli government. While residents are by no means obligated to partake in any activity, the lack of services and amenities in East Jerusalem make the ones offered by the CCS appealing. Shlomo (2017) has argued that the governmentalization of services in East Jerusalem, i.e., the encroachment of Israeli sovereignty into different life spheres there through service provision, is a political process that furthers Israeli control and attempts to consolidate the asymmetrical power relations in the city. In this sense, *limited urban citizenship* can be seen as 'dark' since it might compromise residents' political standpoint to some extent.

However, while many view the CCs in East Jerusalem as a 'top-down' control mechanism, we wish to shed light on the emancipatory aspects of this institution. We find that some CCs do take a leadership role in advocating for their communities and securing their needs. These CC participants actively engage despite their stigmatization as 'collaborators' or 'normalizers' of the occupation, at steep personal and political cost, and

demonstrate agency and savvy as they work to change the political situation from within the system. As Braier (2013) notes with regard to East Jerusalem, local participation in processes such as urban planning does not necessarily constitute a direct resistance to the hegemonic power relations in the city, but can be interpreted as a form of quiet encroachment (Bayat 2000) utilized for the improvement of daily life. Similarly, we suggest that while the involvement of the CCs does not radically transform power-relations in Jerusalem, it does provide a meaningful space for residents' engagement. In so doing, it does not tame alternative forms of mobilization, but rather serves as vehicle for greater representation of East Jerusalemites in city politics. This limited urban citizenship might not come close to more radical forms of insurgent citizenship (Holston 2009) since it does not entail claiming Palestinian national collective rights. However, even this limited political space is significant in the agency and empowerment it may bring to the engaged residents.

Urban citizenship in a non-democratic context

While most research about urban citizenship to date has focused on liberal democracies, less is known about different government structures (Gillespie and Nguyen 2019). By focusing on East Jerusalem's gray space (Avni and Yiftachel 2014), we test the meaning of urban citizenship in the absence of national citizenship—despite the fact that the State of Israel is very much present in the lives of East Jerusalemite Palestinians. The literature on CCs has emphasized issues of contested representation (Jun and Musso 2013; Park, Mosley, and Grogan 2018) and focused mostly on differences resulting from socioeconomic status and class, yet not much has been explored with regard to ethno-nationalism and contested sovereignty. Importantly, the East Jerusalem case rejects the

hegemony of neoliberalism as the dominant force that shapes urban citizenship, pointing instead to other logics such as ethnicity, nationalism, and religion (Yiftachel 2016). The Jerusalem example also stresses the significance of everyday practices, dilemmas, and agencies that shape everyday life in the shadow of the overarching conflict (Selimovic 2019; Greenberg Raanan and Avni 2020).

Our findings concur with the perception of urban citizenship as a *process* rather than a fixed status. We suggest that urban citizenship is both membership in society and a spectrum of everyday formal and informal practices that help residents participate in local politics, improve their quality of life, and get recognition of their identity and day-to-day needs. Jerusalem, like other cities, is marked by segregation, oppression, and violence (Secor 2004; Rokem, Weiss, and Miodownik 2018; Duru 2019; Bhavnani et al. 2014). Therefore, the citizenship process is fragile, fragmented, and inconsistent (Blokland et al. 2015; Millstein 2017). Nonetheless, it slowly takes place. By viewing urban citizenship as a partial and contradictory process, we do not wish to strip it of its liberating potential. As some scholars have noted, the urban scale has some potential in creating a shared and peaceful living (Bollens 2007; Hays 2010; Yiftachel 2016; Avni 2020). Instead, we demonstrate that in the reality of a violent, asymmetrical conflict, such as in East Jerusalem, urban citizenship is structurally limited. In such contexts, pockets of participation such as the ones we have described—services, community organization and political representation—are important forms of collective engagement and are worthy of further attention. In examining such practices, we must be vigilant of the limits of urban citizenship, whereby the pursuit for urban rights sometimes diverts from, or distorts, the accomplishment of national rights.

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